

CARPETS AS REPRESENTATORS OF UZBEKISTAN HISTORY AND CULTURE

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***Annotation:** Human hands are capable of creating wonders. Precious art samples, such as handicraft materials, sculpture, painting, music amaze us from the origin of life on Earth and still make us think to realize what lies within our souls. Carpet making is also an exceptional sample of handmade miracles. It shows unique history of the nation, preserves traditions and culture to deliver among generations, represents people's imagination, hopes and values. This article discusses Uzbek carpet making history, its significance on national and international level and the process to bring one into life.*

***Key words:** Carpet weaving, culture and traditions, colors, value, wool, silk, cotton, dye, manufacturing, carpet workshops, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and Ferghana style of carpets.*

*I do regard spinning and weaving as a necessary
part of any national system of education.*

Mahatma Gandhi

The Uzbek carpet is an astonishing creative piece of art. Rainbow colored nature of the ancient eastern culture is inscribed on carpets: pure white as beautiful clouds in the sky, vibrant green color of mountain fir trees, and emerald shadow of the sky on crystal clear lakes, apple like red and royal purple colors or yellow like leaves of generous autumn – all the colors drawn with strong inspiration and fantasy can be found in Uzbek national carpets.

Carpets are widely used as household items in Uzbekistan. They keep the house warm and even can serve as a noise protection tool when hang on the walls. Probably, every single house in Uzbekistan owns several carpets. They are inseparable part of house decoration regardless the location, shape or type of the house. Carpets cover the floor, decorate the walls and are always valued not only for their practical uses, but also for artistic worth.

Khiva style ready carpets

The art of Uzbek carpet weaving was originated long time ago. Uzbek carpets show an ancient variety of decorative art, which was praised in folklore, classical literary and historical works. Usually their design has simple geometric forms. Many exceptional samples are placed to museums. It is usually a symbol of a family's wealth and prosperity. Especially, during wedding celebrations, embroidered carpets played a significant role. They decorated houses beautifully, and mainly were exchanged as valuable wedding presents.

Preparing process of carpet can seem to be a very time consuming and complicated, besides, it demands big patience. Usually people collaborate in groups to complete the product.

Ornaments of Bukhara style carpet

Some people pick small stones and chips from the wool, some others beat the wool with sticks, while the third group can be busy carding it, the fourth may spin, the fifth group of workers dye and the next class of craftsmen weave a carpet. All the different movements joining up to form made a certain rhythm. The classical Uzbek carpet retains its archaic features both in terms of aesthetics and manufacturing technology: it is woven on a horizontal loom with a narrow beam, in separate strips/panels, which are then sewn into a solid canvas.

Fergana style carpet making process

In Uzbekistan, each region has its own music, melody and special songs and dances, which had from the very ancient times been connected with carpet weaving. The carpet weaving centers carefully preserve sketches of ancient national drawings, which traditionally keep Central Asian symbols. Every region has unique

exceptional style of carpet making, for example, there are Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and Ferghana style of carpets.

In almost all regions of Uzbekistan, there are many small carpet workshops where the masters weave carpets by hand. Home carpet making is also widely developed. Carpets differ in color and ornament depending on the region of Uzbekistan. For example, black, red and blue tones are more prevalent in Samarkand carpets. Long-pile Bukhara carpets are full of multicolor patterns. In the Ferghana valley, carpets have red and blue lines. Specifics of Khiva usually carpets have flower and leaf shapes. Mostly carpets in Uzbekistan are usually woven from wool, cotton, and much less often from silk threads. Special attention should be paid to silk carpets. According to some myths, carpets which have images of sun, talismans and argali horns hold magical meaning; they are intended by design to protect its possessor from harm and bring household good luck and wealth.

Surkhandarya style carpets

Carpets reflect long and rich history of Uzbekistan. Shapes and colors are chosen masterly and weaved harmoniously and they represent lifestyle of the nation, hopes for the future, deep respect to the past.

The late medieval Uzbek carpet is a unique cultural monument that was developed over the course of centuries. It has become even more valuable in the

context of the disappearance of nomadism as a civilizational phenomenon. In her time, ethnographer Balkis Karmysheva proved that the “nomadic steppe” was not only outside of Transoxiana, but also “inside itself.” The carpet, as an expression of the creative potential of Uzbek tribal groups, is an invaluable source that sheds light on the history and artistic ideals of the steppe world, which was an important part of Uzbekistan’s cultural heritage.

After undergoing a decline for most of the 20th century, carpet production in Uzbekistan is now having something of a resurgence. However, the modern products made in various private factories are often far from authentic traditions. A real Uzbek carpet remains a stranger in the bosom of its own culture. Only in a number of provinces, such as Baysun in Surkhandarya, is this longstanding art still alive. However, there are also clear signs of its decline. Creating a modern brand of authentic Uzbek carpets is a crucial task of our time.

Production of silk carpets is being revived in Samarkand. The Uzbek-Afghan joint venture "Afgan-Bukhara-Samarkand" was established here, the main goal of which is to improve the production of silk carpets in Uzbekistan. The entire production process - uncoiling cocoons, making dyes, dyeing threads, and finally textiles-takes place at the enterprise itself. Only natural dyes of local origin - green peel of walnut, pomegranate, madder, the color of the yellow are used to make carpets. The finished carpet is extremely thin and at the same time durable. The quality of the work is very high, but the main thing is the decorative character of the material itself, that is why the silk carpet is valued so highly. Silk carpets are also produced in Bukhara, Margilan, and Khiva.

It is evident that many tourists from European, American, Asian and other countries highly value Uzbekistan national carpets. They often visit carpet workshops, observe and witness carpet making process with high level of eagerness and enthusiasm take photos of the process, ask several questions constantly and even buy and bring to their own countries as gifts or house decorations.

I can confidently say that, Uzbekistan carpet industry has a bright future. There is always great demand to such unique inspirational hand made products all around the world, surely, there always will be. They are created by sincere and kindhearted Uzbek people with love, dedication, deep respect to the national culture and traditions pouring from the bottom of their souls.

Uzbekistan carpets always represented rich culture, values and history of the nation. They still are keeping their high reputation as handmade art in this technology directed era and even are evolving their color, shape, durability and assortment.

References

1. https://centralasiaadventures.com/en/kazakhstan/uzbekistan/carpets_of_uzbekistan.html
2. <https://thehighasia.com/uzbekistan-carpets-history-and-traditions/>
3. <https://voicesoncentralasia.org/carpets-in-uzbekistan-history-and-traditions/>
4. Photos by Google